

Concept note and outline for D4.9: Analysing Just Transformations

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Title: Deliverable 4.9: Just Transformations – Briefing on mainstreaming restoration of freshwater-related ecosystems whilst **leaving no-one behind**

Table of Contents

Contents

Table of Contents	2
1 Introduction	5
1.1 Purpose.....	5
1.2 Focus.....	5
1.3 Target audience	5
2 What is transformation and just transformation in mainstreaming NbS.....	5
2.1 Dimensions of justice	6
2.2 Research questions	6
2.3 Research questions interconnections: disentangling the complexity	8
3 Methodology and Data requirements	9
3.1 Data collection and sources (to be revised)	9
3.2 Data Management – Will be removed when writing the deliverable	13
3.3 Data analysis (to be revised when writing deliverable)	13
3.4 Workplan and responsibilities – Will be removed when writing the deliverable	14
3.5 Limitations	15
4 Integration of just transformation findings across 19 case studies	15
4.1 Representation: What are the composition and patterns of stakeholders engaged in MERLIN case study activities?	15
4.2 Procedure: What are the procedures and practices for involving stakeholders?	16
4.3 Distribution: What are the distributive implications for the case study stakeholders?	16
5 Justice in action in freshwater NbS – reflections on nine case studies.....	17
5.1 CS01 Kvorning wetland rewetting DK	18
5.1.1 Context and stakeholder landscape	18
5.1.2 What issue needed attention?	18
5.1.3 How stakeholder engagement evolved?	18
5.1.4 Outcomes and benefits	18
5.1.5 Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?	18
5.2 CS02 Deba barrier removal ES.....	18
5.2.1 Context and stakeholder landscape	19
5.2.2 What issue needed attention?	19
5.2.3 How stakeholder engagement evolved?	19
5.2.4 Outcomes and benefits	19
5.2.5 Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?	19

5.3	CS04 Room for the Rhine NL	19
5.3.1	Context and stakeholder landscape	19
5.3.2	What issue needed attention?	19
5.3.3	How stakeholder engagement evolved?	19
5.3.4	Outcomes and benefits.....	19
5.3.5	Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?	19
5.4	CS05 Kampinos wetland rewetting PL.....	19
5.4.1	Context and stakeholder landscape	19
5.4.2	What issue needed attention?	19
5.4.3	How stakeholder engagement evolved?	19
5.4.4	Outcomes and benefits.....	19
5.4.5	Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?	19
5.5	CS07a Danube floodplain restoration AT.....	20
5.5.1	Context and stakeholder landscape	20
5.5.2	What issue needed attention?	20
5.5.3	How stakeholder engagement evolved?	20
5.5.4	Outcomes and benefits.....	20
5.5.5	Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?	20
5.6	CS09 Tisza floodplain rewetting HU	20
5.6.1	Context and stakeholder landscape	20
5.6.2	What issue needed attention?	20
5.6.3	How stakeholder engagement evolved?	20
5.6.4	Outcomes and benefits.....	20
5.6.5	Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?	20
5.7	CS12 Lima River forest restoration PT	20
5.7.1	Context and stakeholder landscape	21
5.7.2	What issue needed attention?	21
5.7.3	How stakeholder engagement evolved?	21
5.7.4	Outcomes and benefits.....	21
5.7.5	Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?	21
5.8	CS15 Tzipori basin restoration IL.....	21
5.8.1	Context and stakeholder landscape	21
5.8.2	What issue needed attention?	21
5.8.3	How stakeholder engagement evolved?	21
5.8.4	Outcomes and benefits.....	21
5.8.5	Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?	21

5.9	CS17 Forth basin restoration UK.....	21
5.9.1	Context and stakeholder landscape	21
5.9.2	What issue needed attention?	21
5.9.3	How stakeholder engagement evolved?	21
5.9.4	Outcomes and benefits.....	21
5.9.5	Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?	21
6	Discussions: Implications for taking just transformation approach	21
6.1	Challenges and opportunities for taking just transformation approach.....	22
6.2	Recommendations	22
6.2.1	For future projects	22
6.2.2	For policy makers and funders.....	22
6.2.3	For researchers.....	22
7	Conclusion.....	22
	References.....	22
	Appendices.....	23
	Annex 1: List of 18 MERLIN case studies	23
	Annex 2: Description of data used and collection process	24

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

- To provide a structured briefing on how Nature-based Solutions (NbS) can be mainstreamed to restore freshwater-related ecosystems while ensuring justice, inclusion, and sustained to deliver societal benefits.
- To present case studies demonstrating how local NbS projects have been implemented with an emphasis on citizen involvement and governance.

1.2 Focus

This task focuses on stakeholder engagement processes across MERLIN's freshwater NbS case studies. The emphasis on stakeholder engagement reflects its central role in enabling just transformations, ensuring inclusive, representative, and equitable governance. As Ibrahim et al. (2025) highlight, improving stakeholder engagement processes – in terms of stakeholder diversity and thoughtful and equitable engagement processes – essential to achieving fair and effective Nature-based Solutions. The analysis will draw on all 18 case studies and the number of case studies to be proposed for illustration. I propose 5 or 6 – 2 for each cluster) studies, selecting those with sufficient and high-quality engagement data for illustration (see Annex). This focus complements Deliverable D4.2, which has already addressed just transformations from the perspective of sectoral engagement.

Note: The product is not full research report, but focussed more on reflections and main implications for future NbS projects.

1.3 Target audience

2 What is transformation and just transformation in mainstreaming NbS

In the context of mainstreaming freshwater Nature-based Solutions (NbS), transformations refer to systemic changes in governance, values, and decision-making processes that enable widespread, sustainable uptake of NbS (Carmen et al., 2024). These transformations are considered just when they actively address social equity by ensuring that decision-making is inclusive (procedural justice), that diverse stakeholder voices are represented (representational justice), and that the costs and benefits of NbS are fairly distributed (distributional justice) (Cousins, 2021; Wijsman & Berbés-Blázquez, 2022).

In the context of this briefing, just transformations mean enhancing the roles of local stakeholders – private, public, NGOs, community groups, etc – whose lived experiences are crucial to equitable NbS implementation (Gionfra et al., 2023; Tallent & Zabala, 2024). This includes co-producing knowledge and embedding these values into freshwater governance structures to ensure that NbS initiatives are not only ecologically sound but also socially inclusive (Boyland et al., 2022; Whitt, 2022).

Our approach reflects a shift from a solely ecological or technical framing of NbS to one that acknowledges power, agency, and diverse worldviews (Carmen et al., 2024). It also aligns with global guidance such as the IPBES framework and the IUCN Global Standard, which emphasize participation, legitimacy, and trade-off negotiations.

Originally, Task 4.2 was framed as “Translating MERLIN case study findings for EU Sectors and EU Just Transitions Policy,” with the aim of linking MERLIN’s empirical findings to EU sectoral strategies and Just Transition objectives, particularly around climate mitigation and adaptation. However, this framing has proven too narrow and potentially misleading. The EU’s Just Transition Policy is focused primarily on the energy transition in carbon-intensive regions, and only a small number of MERLIN case studies are located within these designated areas. Connecting MERLIN’s work to this policy would require substantial additional research and risk confusion when engaging with EU institutions. Importantly, a dedicated deliverable has already addressed sectoral engagement processes in detail, reducing the need to duplicate this focus within Task 4.2.

The shift to “Just Transformations” more accurately reflects both the direction of the task and MERLIN’s conceptual framework. Rather than centring on energy or climate transitions, the revised focus addresses the systemic governance changes needed to mainstream freshwater Nature-based Solutions (NbS) in a socially just way. It emphasizes representation, inclusive participation, and fair distribution of NbS benefits and burdens—issues especially relevant to the local and territorial scales at which MERLIN operates. The reframing also enables stronger integration with other WP4 tasks and makes use of rich stakeholder engagement data already generated across the project to explore how freshwater NbS can contribute to equitable, place-based transformations.

2.1 Dimensions of justice

Just transformation can be addressed differently given the diverse framework of justice. However, justice in Nature-based Solutions (NbS) is not just about ensuring positive environmental outcomes but also about making sure these interventions do not deepen existing inequalities. NbS involves ensuring diverse knowledge and perspectives are represented, shaping governance procedures to ensure there are deeper involvement, redistributing costs and benefits equitably. For this reason, three core dimensions (Cousins, 2021; Wijsman & Berbés-Blázquez, 2022) of justice are explored:

1. **Representative Justice** – Valuing diverse knowledge systems, cultural perspectives, and the rights of marginalized groups across sectoral, administrative scales and territories.
2. **Procedural Justice** – Ensuring meaningful participation and decision-making power for all affected stakeholders.
3. **Distributional Justice** – Ensuring fair allocation of benefits and burdens of ecosystem restoration.

2.2 Research questions

The overall research question is how does the MERLIN project’s approach to engagement of stakeholders in freshwater NbS shape and support just transformations? The specific questions are grouped based on the dimensions of justice.

1. What are the composition and patterns of stakeholders engaged in MERLIN case study activities? **This question aims to assess the representation in the cases, so that the framing of problems and solutions considers the perspectives of all affected groups, including cultural and social differences.**

- a. Types of stakeholders engaged. This will help know who were engaged and the reasons why they were engaged. We will also consider who were approached but declined to participate.
 - i. These data will come from stakeholder mapping in excel template, inclusivity indicators, ladder of participation; SAT, CSB stakeholder excel... Stakeholder types include public, private (commercial, investor, etc), NGO, Network, community group, others (to directly relate to the first 5 types)
 - b. Analysis will consider these patterns by a range of factors
2. What are the procedures and practices for involving stakeholders?
 - a. How were the participation of various stakeholder groups organized, what forms and levels of engagement exist?
 - b. What were modes of engagement; how were stakeholders selected, and how are interactions between stakeholders designed, what was the purpose of interactions?
 3. What are the distributive implications for the CS stakeholders?
 - a. Were the costs and benefits of NbS implementation clearly identified, and was a participatory process used to determine who gained and who lost?
 - b. How were processes established to reduce and manage negative impacts in collaboration with local communities?

The above questions are identified bearing in mind that there are multiple criteria for analysing each justice dimension. Therefore, the identified criterion for this briefing is based on the data availability instead of attempting to analyse all criteria associated with each dimension. The specific criteria

Table 1. Justice dimensions, associated research questions and criteria and concepts for analysis

Note: While there are many criteria for each RQ, we will prioritise based on data availability. Instead of focusing on each sub-research questions, we should focus on looking at how these criteria are manifested whether, quantitatively or qualitatively or both.

Justice dimension	Key research	Criteria/concept for analysis	Selected References
Representation	What are the composition and patterns of stakeholders engaged in MERLIN case study activities?	<p>Main criterion is to assess if representation covers broad spectrum of stakeholder types affected by the NbS project. Specifically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence of clear procedure for identifying different types of stakeholders affected by the project, ensuring that local communities are represented. • Embracing diversity, ensuring that stakeholder types cut across different cultural and knowledge domains {van der Jagt, 2023 #1043}. • Opportunities for minority groups to be represented. • Approach to avoid discrimination towards certain groups (Note: need to discuss if this should be included or not) 	

Procedure	What are the procedures and practices for involving stakeholders?	<p>Main criterion is to assess opportunities for active/deep involvement so that stakeholders can influence the design and implementation process as opposed to tokenistic approach. Specifically, we will assess:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence of a clear and open stakeholder selection process. • Presence of measures to encourage participation of minority groups including local communities. • Promoting deeper levels of engagement (involvement, collaboration, empowerment beyond) tokenistic levels (informing, consulting) • Having more interactive, multiple mediums of communication (e.g. meetings, interviews, workshops) beyond emails, newsletters, etc. • Establishing feedback and grievance resolution mechanism. 	
Distribution	What are the distributive implications for the CS stakeholders?	<p>Broad criteria are to understand how issues of cost and benefits related to the projects where approached. This is not just financial cost.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broad understanding of cost and benefits associated with the projects. • Presence of clear procedure for identifying cost and benefits associated with projects. • Identification of procedures for reducing and managing negative impacts including compensations. • Acknowledgement of diverse definition of benefits and costs (e.g. provisioning, regulating and cultural) so that the powerful voices are heard. 	

2.3 Research questions interconnections: disentangling the complexity

The justice dimensions are cross-cutting and interdependent. For example, an NbS project may be procedurally just (involving public consultation) but still distributionally unjust if benefits remain concentrated among the wealthy.

Justice in NbS interventions is not a **set of separate categories but a web of interconnections** where distributive, procedural, and representative justice continuously shape and reinforce one another. Wijsman and Berbés-Blázquez (2022) describes the interconnections as follows:

- **Who benefits and who bears the costs (distributive justice) is shaped by who gets to participate (procedural justice).** If decision-making spaces are exclusionary, then certain groups may never access the benefits of NbS projects.
- **Who participates is influenced by whose voices are recognised as legitimate (representative justice).** If minority groups and local knowledge systems are

undervalued, their exclusion from governance structures can lead to unfair distribution of resources and benefits.

- **The way resources are distributed affects who can engage in governance.** If communities lack access to funding, information, or decision-making power, their ability to influence NbS implementation is severely limited.

Because of these interdependencies, addressing justice in NbS requires an integrated, rather than fragmented, approach. Overlooking one-dimension risks deepening inequalities in others. Ensuring just transformations in freshwater restoration means designing governance structures that guarantee inclusive participation, policies that recognize diverse knowledge systems, and financial mechanisms that equitably distribute resources. Without such interconnected solutions, NbS risks reinforcing existing injustices rather than delivering meaningful transformation.

3 Methodology and Data requirements

3.1 Data collection and sources (Can be revised to align with own project)

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To ensure depth and clarity, the analysis will focus on a selected sample of five case studies. These are chosen based on the availability and richness of relevant data, and their ability to illustrate the diversity of approaches and experiences across the MERLIN programme.

Table 2. Research questions and associated data sources

Note: All data that are needed for the task have been collate a single [D4.9 Data folder](#) (accessible to Hutton Team only). Decision on case study with best data will be made in conjunction with screening the case study summaries generated by Matthew and Eleanor. See section 3.2 – Data Management – for further information. For how the data will be synthesized and summarised follow this guide: [2025-04-14 Data Analysis, collation \u0026 memo guide.docx](#)

Research Question	Data source	How to use the data and do analysis	Who can help
<p>1. What are the composition and patterns of stakeholders engaged in MERLIN case study activities? case study activities?</p> <p>Main criterion is to assess if representation covers broad spectrum of stakeholder types affected by the NbS project. Specifically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence of clear procedure for identifying different 	<p>CS Stakeholder mapping</p> <p>Also in Next cloud</p> <p>Stakeholder mapping should be complemented by the CSB annual workshop minutes.</p>	<p>CS stakeholder mapping excels templates presented by each CS. Help to assess the common stakeholder types initially identified and rationale for identifying those stakeholders. Can also help to know the diversity of stakeholders. Can help know which minority stakeholder groups were identified.</p> <p>Here we can say there is clear procedure for identifying stakeholders since all CS did CS mapping. However, this will not mean everyone identified is involved.</p>	<p>Individual CS – managed and consolidated by WULS</p> <p>Not sure WULS are willing to do that, so we have to have the summary ourselves.</p> <p>Hassan and Rebecca to screen each and provide overall</p>

<p>types of stakeholders affected by the project, ensuring that local communities are represented.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Embracing diversity, ensuring that stakeholder types cut across different cultural and knowledge domains. • Opportunities for minority groups to be represented. • Approach to avoid discrimination towards certain groups (Note: need to discuss if this should be included or not) 			overview (did presentation on this in 22 consortium meeting)
	<p>Inclusivity indicator. On OneDrive. More importantly, Axels preliminary statistics are here in onedrive. We need to as Axel fo latest statistics.</p>	<p>Counts (quantitative) of stakeholder types being involved in excel template. This will help us know how many of each stakeholder types (including the specific types) engaged. This can be compared with the stakeholder mapping to see the differences. It can also be compared with MiniSAT to understand what the stakeholders themselves say.</p>	<p>Individual CS – data collected by WULS and NIVA. Analysis already available and will be used as part of this.</p>
	<p>MiniSAT. The individual CS results as well as summarised key messages are in OneDrive following the link provided above.</p>	<p>Help assess perceptions of stakeholders about involvement of wider stakeholders covering all the criterion for analysis. Questions about inclusivity are good for this part. It can be both qualitative and quantitative and can help compare and contrast with what is reported in the inclusivity indicator.</p>	<p>JHI</p> <p>Hassan will use the analysis already generated via Qualtrics. Open-text responses already in Nvivo and can already refer to.</p>
	<p>IUCN Full SAT – We will rely on 2023 Full SAT and not 2022. The summary of the 2023 submissions by Pawel in OneDrive. The individual CS submission is also in same folder. An excel file containing the open all text</p>	<p>Rating and open-text responses of CS regarding various criteria including 5.3 (whether direct and indirect stakeholders are identified and involved) and 5.2 and 5.4 (to help understand if there is opportunity for minority groups and understand ways to avoid discrimination – thus if participation s-based equality and respect for all stakeholders irrespective of their status) Each file is in excel.</p>	<p>JHI</p> <p>Overall synthesis already generated by Pawel. There is no synthesis for the specific criteria. Hassan can request Pawel to do that, but it might be to do that ourselves so as to beat time. Hassan already combined all</p>

	responses are also upload.		the open-text responses in excel and can easily generate an overview of findings.
	RSP (regional strategic stakeholders)	RSPs are in word or PDF. According to Maria there weren't much stakeholder engagement for the RSPs but there was a quick summary. The RSP Self-assessment does not provide much information either. But Chapter 3 of the RSPs focus on stakeholders. It's more about description of stakeholders and not about engagement process so not sure we include it. We can use RSPs example of stakeholder involvement in specific aspect of mainstreaming NbS, but not sure the data is strong enough.	Individual CS. Consolidated by Deltares and SYKE. There previously said they can't provide much as they didn't do much of stakeholder activities, but we can approach them to let them know.
2. What are the procedures and practices of involving stakeholders? Main criteria are to assess opportunities for active/deep involvement as opposed to tokenistic approach: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder selection process Forms and levels (informing, consulting, involving, collaborating, empowering) of engagement Presence of measures to encourage participation of minority groups, including local communities. Promoting deeper levels of engagement (involvement, collaboration, empowerment beyond) 	CSBs and ladder action: The summarised presentation by Mateusz S can be used but we need to ask we they could write a session for us. Mateusz M indicated they still haven't sorted out their paper, so need to know the implications.	Help assess the levels of engagement to evaluate if engagement was deep or tokenistic. This will be checked for the different types of stakeholders identified in RQ1 and will help know how local communities in particular are engaged.	Individual CS – managed and consolidated by WULS Hassan to Ask Mateusz if they can give brief overview and let us know which CS best offers examples. Not sure as the Mateusz said they still have sorted out the publications.
	Full-SAT	Criterion 5.1 will help understand the rating for understanding the feedback and grievance resolution mechanisms. Rely on textual explanations and ratings.	As previously mentioned for Pawel. But Hassan will do.

<p>tokenistic levels (informing, consulting)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having more interactive, multiple mediums of communication (e.g. meetings, interviews, workshops) beyond emails, newsletters, etc • Establishing feedback and grievance resolution mechanism. 	MiniSAT	Help assess the stakeholder perceptions, views and the recurring themes about how they were involved and whether they feel engaged or not.	JHI – We can use Qualtrics and excel to generate the qual analysis and do content analysis of the open text responses.
	Inclusivity indicator	Help assess levels and means of engagement (e.g., Information on website on contacts and how to get involved, signage onsite on contacts and how to get involved, consultation on measures with case-study board, formal public consultation on measures, etc.). This can be compared with the ladder action as well as what stakeholders say.	Individual CS – data collected by WULS and NIVA
	RSP (regional strategic stakeholders)	To assess whether involvement in the RSP development process were deep. This part of the data looks weak.	Individual CS. Consolidated by Deltares and SYKE
	Sept 24 consortium meeting Lighthouse The text from the Mirror Board is here	There is not much information provided, but they give about a sentence description of participatory implementation process for each CS. This will give a rough idea about how the CS feel implementation has been participatory.	Hutton.
<p>3. What are the distributive implications for the CS stakeholders?</p> <p>Focus more on process of distributions rather than outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Processes for identifying cost and benefits • Broad understanding of cost and benefits associated with the projects • Process for reducing and managing negative impacts including compensations • Acknowledgement of diverse definition of benefits and costs (e.g. provisioning, regulating 	Full SAT	Criterion 1 helps understand beneficiaries and social challenges addressed and the well-being outcomes identified. Criterion 4 (4.1 – 4.4) will insights about how cost was identified. Will include ratings and open-text responses from each CS. Criterion 6 will also provide insights on how rights are managed and compensations available. Criterion 7 will give insights on how possible negative impacts of the NbS are managed.	As mentioned earlier. We can ask Pawel for the specific criteria. But Hassan can do if needed particularly focusing on the open-text responses.
	MiniSAT	Stakeholders' perception of about the cost and benefits and assessment of grievances regarding the NbS projects. Also, analyse if stakeholders understand the risks management plans and if there are of grievances.	JHI as mentioned earlier.
	Inclusivity Indicator	Helps assess the CS rating of whether the projects address the core challenges faced, if stakeholders feel positive about the NbS	WULS and JHI

and cultural) so that the powerful voices are heard.	RSP (regional strategic stakeholders)	As mentioned above in RQ2.	Individual CS. Consolidated by Deltares and SYKE
All questions	Overall CS summaries and informal interviews with CS leads. We can start contacting the CS leads once we agree on which CS to use.	This will cover all the RQs and focus on answering question that are not easily understood by	JHI

3.2 Data Management

To support a clear and coordinated analysis process, all the data sources will be collated into a single shared folder, replacing the current system of dispersed hyperlinks and separate locations. While the main data overview table and the ‘Data Requirement and Availability’ file currently contain links to individual datasets, these files will now serve as entry points into a centralised folder where all relevant materials will be stored.

Each dataset will be grouped by data type (e.g. stakeholder mapping, inclusivity indicator, MiniSAT) (sub-folders already created) and accompanied by a synthesis file that consolidates the relevant content for analysis. This will make it easier to review, compare, and extract insights across case studies without repeatedly navigating raw inputs.

A tracking file will be maintained to monitor data availability, completeness, and the status of synthesis and analysis across case studies and data types. Rebecca is also reviewing each case study’s data to identify which offer the strongest evidence for inclusion in the final deliverable.

This approach is intended to ensure a more efficient workflow, reduce duplication, and allow for flexible analysis while staying within the project’s time constraints.

3.3 Data analysis (to be revised when writing deliverable)

The analysis follows a pragmatic and focused approach, shaped by time constraints and the briefing-style format of this deliverable. Rather than undertaking in-depth or systematic analysis of all datasets, we prioritise extracting the most relevant and illustrative insights across the three research questions.

Given the variety of formats – ranging from structured numerical data to free-text narratives – different tools will be used for different types of data. Structured and semi-structured data (e.g. stakeholder mapping templates, inclusivity indicators, SAT ratings, CSB summaries) will primarily be analysed in Excel, allowing for basic quantitative summaries, comparisons across case studies, and the development of visual overview matrices. These will support pattern recognition and data triangulation.

Unstructured qualitative data (e.g. open-text responses from MiniSAT and Full-SAT, workshop notes, and interview summaries) would ideally be coded systematically using NVivo, but due to time limitations, we will instead use a lighter thematic content review. This may involve keyword searches, clustering by recurring themes, and basic annotation – conducted directly in Word, Excel, or through NVivo’s auto-coding functions if useful. The focus will be on extracting illustrative quotes and identifying dominant patterns rather than comprehensive coding.

For the datasets are held or managed externally – for instance, the ladder of engagement and inclusivity indicator – colleagues who led the work will be invited to provide the required summary statistics or key findings. If these are not available in time, we will extract and synthesise the relevant insights ourselves using available documentation.

To manage this complexity, a summary matrix will be developed to track the availability, coverage, and analytical value of each data source per case study. This will help ensure consistency in interpretation and support integration across qualitative and quantitative streams.

3.4 Workplan and responsibilities – Will be removed when writing the deliverable

Date	Activity to be completed	Who is responsible
Mid-April	Finalise concept note	
	Agree on the data to be used	
	Identify CS which best help analyse each research question for specific data	
	Contact MERLIN partners (Mateusz, Pawel, Axel, Nadine? Maria?) about their contribution and request for necessary data and if they could write something.	
Mid-May	Initial screening, synthesis of data and generating memos and insights for research questions	
	Meeting to check progress and plan to fill any gaps.	
	Identify CS to use for illustration	
	Decide if ethics application is needed and submit it.	
	Discuss plan for interviews and develop interview guide and schedule invitations	
End of May	Finalise data synthesis and memo generation, fill any gaps identified.	
	Plan for writing the deliverable	
June	Start drafting the deliverable	
	Notify co-authors and CS about the deliverable and making time available for review. Email targeted depending on the role	
Early July	Complete initial draft and share with co-authors and CS for review. Targeted in email based on role	
	Start putting on template while waiting for feedback	
Mid July	Address comments and finalise	

End July	Final version shared with coordinators, Steering Group, Rob St John etc	
End August	Finalise the material and submit to coordinators for uploading	

3.5 Limitations

The data available vary significantly across case studies in terms of depth, format, and qualitative richness. As a result, the level of analysis and emphasis differs across cases. Some datasets, particularly those from RSPs, are relatively limited in terms of stakeholder engagement detail.

Additionally, given the briefing-style format of this deliverable, it is not feasible to provide detailed insights from every case study. Instead, a targeted set of eight case studies will be used for illustrative purposes. While these provide valuable examples, they do not represent the full range of contexts or practices across all MERLIN case studies.

A full methodological account, including analytical tools, data screening criteria, and case selection rationale, will be provided in the annex.

4 Integration of just transformation findings across 19 case studies

Here will give overall integration based on dimensions of just transformation addressing the three questions without going deep. **Please, refer to guideline for specifically what is needed. 1-2 paragraph introduction of this chapter**

- Stick to **analytical writing** don't list all the case studies or indicators.
- Use **1-2 examples maximum** to support a point. Choose those that are vivid and representative.
- End with a **short reflection** on what the findings imply for that justice dimension in the context of NbS (Nature-based Solutions).
- Avoid data tables or indicator codes this section should **complement** detailed annexes or indicator summaries, not duplicate them.
-

4.1 Representation: What are the composition and patterns of stakeholders engaged in MERLIN case study activities?

Who is responsible for this chapter?	
Who will support?	
Page limit	Maximum 2 pages
Overall criterion	to assess if representation covers broad spectrum of stakeholder types affected by the NbS project. So, analysis should aim to provide the types of stakeholders engaged across all the CS studies, not for specific CS.
What indicators to focus on:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Present a synthesis of the types of stakeholders represented across case studies (e.g. public sector, NGOs, local communities, private/commercial actors, minority or underrepresented groups). • Discuss how stakeholder identification was approached, e.g. any systematic procedures to ensure inclusivity or ensure local actors are not overlooked.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflect on diversity: Were efforts made to include groups with different forms of knowledge (scientific, local, indigenous)? Cite examples where this was done well. • Note whether any minority or vulnerable groups were mentioned and how they were represented (or not). • If relevant, mention whether measures to avoid bias or discrimination in representation were identified — but only if supported by evidence.
General tips to keep it short and concise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stick to analytical writing – don't list all the case studies or indicators. • Use 1–3 examples maximum to support a point. Choose those that are vivid and representative. • End with a short reflection on what the findings imply for that justice dimension in the context of NbS (Nature-based Solutions). • Avoid data tables or indicator codes – this section should complement detailed annexes or indicator summaries, not duplicate them.

4.2 Procedure: What are the procedures and practices for involving stakeholders?

Who is responsible for this chapter?	
Who will support?	
Page limit	Maximum 2 pages
Overall criterion	to assess opportunities for active/deep involvement so that stakeholders can influence the design and implementation process as opposed to tokenistic approach. Therefore, analysis should focus on presenting how the participation of various stakeholder groups organized, what forms and levels of engagement exist.
What indicators to focus on:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyse how stakeholders were engaged across different stages of the project (planning, design, implementation). Did it go beyond consultation? • Describe the depth of engagement (informing, consulting, involving, collaborating, empowering). Was the engagement meaningful or procedural? • Highlight whether there was a clear, transparent stakeholder selection process in place in some case studies. • Discuss tools and methods of engagement used: Were there interactive or face-to-face meetings, co-design workshops, or just newsletters/emails? • Briefly mention whether there were any mechanisms for feedback, complaint, or grievance resolution, if this emerged in the data. • Flag if any efforts were made to include marginalised or hard-to-reach groups in more participatory ways.
General tips to keep it short and concise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stick to analytical writing – don't list all the case studies or indicators. • Use 1–3 examples maximum to support a point. Choose those that are vivid and representative. • End with a short reflection on what the findings imply for that justice dimension in the context of NbS (Nature-based Solutions). • Avoid data tables or indicator codes – this section should complement detailed annexes or indicator summaries, not duplicate them.

4.3 Distribution: What are the distributive implications for the case study stakeholders?

Who is responsible for this chapter?	
Who will support?	
Page limit	Maximum 2 pages
Overall criterion	Understand how issues of cost and benefits related to the projects were approached. This is not just monetary cost or in quantitative terms , but we want to understand if the costs and benefits of NbS implementation clearly identified, and if was a participatory process used to determine who gained and who lost?
What indicators to focus on:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss whether case studies provided a broad understanding of benefits and costs (e.g. environmental, social, cultural — not only economic). • Explore whether benefits and burdens were clearly identified and to whom they might accrue or affect negatively (e.g. landowners losing productive land, public gaining recreation space). • Mention if any processes existed for identifying and managing costs/benefits, including conflict mitigation or compensation schemes. • Reflect on how diverse values (e.g. cultural heritage, livelihoods, ecosystem services) were considered in discussions of impacts. • If data allow flag whether the project tried to balance or redistribute impacts in an equitable way.
General tips to keep it short and concise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stick to analytical writing – don't list all the case studies or indicators. • Use 1–3 examples maximum to support a point. Choose those that are vivid and representative. • End with a short reflection on what the findings imply for that justice dimension in the context of NbS (Nature-based Solutions). • Avoid data tables or indicator codes – this section should complement detailed annexes or indicator summaries, not duplicate them.

5 Justice in action in freshwater NbS – reflections on nine case studies

Here, we want to tell a story of transformation from each selected case study, through the lens of justice, particularly as it relates to stakeholder engagement and governance. The goal is not to repeat general project summaries, but to highlight the lived experiences, key decisions, and moments where justice, representation, procedure and distribution (or wasn't) part of the transformation. We're especially interested in where and how your project addressed:

- Representation – Who had a voice, and who was included?
- Procedural Justice – How fair, transparent, or inclusive were the processes?
- Distributional Equity – Who gained (or lost) from the changes, and how were benefits or risks shared?

See the sections for structuring the below:

1. Context and stakeholder landscape	Describe the socio-environmental of the project. Who were the key actors? What legacies (social, political, ecological) framed stakeholder relations and the project.
2. What issue needed attention?	Identify a key challenge or opportunities needing some response to be able to implement the project. Was there a point where something wasn't working or needed to be done differently? Did anyone raise concerns about fairness, participation, or benefits? Was there a moment of decision, difficulty, or opportunity?

3. How stakeholder engagement evolved?	Describe the practices, approaches, or changes you adopted in response to the issues. How were stakeholders brought in more meaningfully? Were specific tools, platforms, or mediators used? Did strategies evolve to foster more equal participation or acknowledge local knowledge or rights? <i>Tip: You can consider talking about representation and procedure, i.e., how you went about planning and conducting stakeholder engagement to ensure balance of representation, procedure and distribution.</i>
4. Outcomes and benefits	Reflect on how the response influenced the project . What changed in the community, environment, or governance? What were the benefits and costs? Were grievances addressed? Did people feel heard or empowered? Were there any unintended results or people left out? <i>Tip: Just transformation doesn't need to be perfect, so acknowledge what worked and what didn't work well.</i>
5. Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?	Conclude with 2–3 clear lessons. What would you advise other practitioners attempting just transformations through stakeholder engagement when implementing NbS? What worked and what didn't work? What might you do differently next time? <i>Tip: Be reflective and offer practical insights.</i>

5.1 CS01 Kvorning wetland rewetting DK

Who is responsible for this chapter?	
Who will support?	
Possible headline topic for guidance	Headline topic could be collective Consent: Voluntary participation and land negotiation
Page limit	Maximum 1 page

5.1.1 Context and stakeholder landscape

5.1.2 What issue needed attention?

5.1.3 How stakeholder engagement evolved?

5.1.4 Outcomes and benefits

5.1.5 Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?

5.2 CS02 Deba barrier removal ES

Who is responsible for this chapter?	
Who will support?	
Possible headline topic for guidance	When River Restoration Meets Cultural Identity: Navigating Civic Resistance and Democratic Deliberation

Page limit	Maximum 1 page
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- 5.2.1 Context and stakeholder landscape
- 5.2.2 What issue needed attention?
- 5.2.3 How stakeholder engagement evolved?
- 5.2.4 Outcomes and benefits
- 5.2.5 Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?

5.3 CS04 Room for the Rhine NL

Who is responsible for this chapter?	
Who will support?	
Possible headline topic for guidance	From protest to partnership: NGOS and state collaboration on the rhine floodplain
Page limit	Maximum 1 page

- 5.3.1 Context and stakeholder landscape
- 5.3.2 What issue needed attention?
- 5.3.3 How stakeholder engagement evolved?
- 5.3.4 Outcomes and benefits
- 5.3.5 Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?

5.4 CS05 Kampinos wetland rewetting PL

Who is responsible for this chapter?	
Who will support?	
Possible headline topic for guidance	Inclusive by Design: Rotating Forums and Stakeholder Networks in a Fragmented Landscape
Page limit	Maximum 1 page

- 5.4.1 Context and stakeholder landscape
- 5.4.2 What issue needed attention?
- 5.4.3 How stakeholder engagement evolved?
- 5.4.4 Outcomes and benefits
- 5.4.5 Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?

5.5 CS07a Danube floodplain restoration AT

Who is responsible for this chapter?	
Who will support?	
Possible headline topic for guidance	Trust and Fairness in Stakeholder Boards: Balancing Inclusion with Sectoral Gaps
Page limit	Maximum 1 page

5.5.1 Context and stakeholder landscape

5.5.2 What issue needed attention?

5.5.3 How stakeholder engagement evolved?

5.5.4 Outcomes and benefits

5.5.5 Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?

5.6 CS09 Tisza floodplain rewetting HU

Who is responsible for this chapter?	
Who will support?	
Possible headline topic for guidance	Restoring with memory: Trade-offs, compensation, and long-term engagement
Page limit	Maximum 1 page

5.6.1 Context and stakeholder landscape

5.6.2 What issue needed attention?

5.6.3 How stakeholder engagement evolved?

5.6.4 Outcomes and benefits

5.6.5 Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?

5.7 CS12 Lima River forest restoration PT

Who is responsible for this chapter?	
Who will support?	
Possible headline topic for guidance	Negotiating Restoration in a Patchwork Landscape: Inclusivity and Trade-offs
Page limit	Maximum 1 page

- 5.7.1 Context and stakeholder landscape
- 5.7.2 What issue needed attention?
- 5.7.3 How stakeholder engagement evolved?
- 5.7.4 Outcomes and benefits
- 5.7.5 Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?

5.8 CS15 Tzipori basin restoration IL

Who is responsible for this chapter?	
Who will support?	
Possible headline topic for guidance	Inclusive water futures in a fragmented landscape: Building trust across diverse communities
Page limit	Maximum 1 page

- 5.8.1 Context and stakeholder landscape
- 5.8.2 What issue needed attention?
- 5.8.3 How stakeholder engagement evolved?
- 5.8.4 Outcomes and benefits
- 5.8.5 Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?

5.9 CS17 Forth basin restoration UK

Who is responsible for this chapter?	
Who will support?	
Possible headline topic for guidance	Steering inclusion through continuity: the role of existing networks in building trust
Page limit	Maximum 1 page

- 5.9.1 Context and stakeholder landscape
- 5.9.2 What issue needed attention?
- 5.9.3 How stakeholder engagement evolved?
- 5.9.4 Outcomes and benefits
- 5.9.5 Lessons – What can others learn from your experience?

6 Discussions: Implications for taking just transformation approach

Who is responsible for this chapter?	
Who will support?	

Page limit	2 pages including recommendations?
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6.1 Challenges and opportunities for taking just transformation approach

Here, we will be 'exploratory/critical and discuss the gaps, problems and issues', touching on patterns and changes as well as differences across sectors, geographies and NbS types.

6.2 Recommendations

6.2.1 For future projects

Lessons for similar NbS and restoration projects 1-2 paragraphs

6.2.2 For policy makers and funders

Lessons for policy makers including national and EU level. Can consider existing EU policies here. 1-2 paragraphs

6.2.3 For researchers

What are the implications for future researchers? 1-2 paragraphs

7 Conclusion

Who is responsible for this chapter?	
Who will support?	
Page limit	1 page

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Appendices

Annex 1: List of 18 MERLIN case studies

No.	Country	Name	Small rivers & their catchment	Large trans-boundary rivers	Peatlands & wetlands
CS01	Denmark	Kvorning wetland rewetting DK			X
CS02	Spain	Deba barrier removal ES	X		
CS03	Sweden	Beaver river engineering SE			X
CS04	the Netherlands	Room for the Rhine NL		X	
CS05	Poland	Kampinos wetland rewetting PL			X
CS06	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Hutovo Blato peatland rewetting BiH			X
CS07 a	Austria	Danube floodplain restoration AT		X	

CS07 b	Hungary	Danube sidearm reconnect HU		X	
CS08	Romania	Danube floodplains reconnect RO		X	
CS09	Hungary	Tisza floodplain rewetting HU		X	
CS10	Germany	Blue Belt Germany DE		X	
CS11	Germany	Emscher basin restoration DE	X		
CS12	Portugal	Lima river forest restoration PT			X
CS13	Portugal	Sorraia river restoration PT	X		
CS14	Finland	Komppasuo peatland rewetting FI			X
CS15	Israel	Tzipori basin restoration IL	X		
CS16	Belgium	Upper Scheldt restoration BE	X		
CS17	United Kingdom	Forth basin restoration UK	X		X
CS18	Portugal	Ervidel river restoration PT	X		

Annex 2: Description of data used and collection process